

The Role of Dubai Government in Supporting Responsible and Sustainable Practices of the Private Sector: A Case Study on the Dubai Chamber of Commerce and Industry

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ABSTRACT: The increasing profile of CSR as a concept in government action linked to the challenges of globalization and economic change in the late 20th century, such as corporate citizenship, and the interrelationships between trade, investment, and sustainable development. The purpose of this study is to provide a deeper understanding of how governments support the practices of social responsibility, by identifying the roles adopted by Dubai government to support and promote the responsible and sustainable business practices in Dubai, via case study approach on Dubai Chamber of Commerce and Industry. The study also aims to monitor and analyze Dubai Chamber's efforts and policies in this regard, in order to draw lessons learned and to make suggestions that can be used to improve the performance of governments and to create pioneering experiments in this area. For data collection of this study, the researcher used a qualitative analysis and case study approach, based on in-depth interviews with those responsible for the Center of Responsible Business (CRB) at Dubai Chamber. The main findings of the case study demonstrate that Dubai Chamber promotes CSR as an opportunity and competitive advantage for business, as it adopts win-win relationship "mutual benefit" with the private sector. It plays different and integral roles (awareness role, regulatory role, legislative role, and endorsing role) to entrench the principle of corporate citizenship and to support businesses to work in a responsible and sustainable manner.

KEYWORDS: corporate citizenship, corporate social responsibility, Dubai government, sustainable development

Introduction

The World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD) has defined corporate social responsibility as "The commitment of business to contribute to sustainable economic development, working with employees, their families, the local community and society to improve their quality of life" (Fox et al. 2002, 1). Moreover, CSR has been defined as a concept whereby companies decide voluntarily to contribute to a better society and cleaner environment (Albareda et al. 2007).

Corporates of all sizes, types, and fields of business are an essential source of economic activity and a vital component of the social fabric, so they drive the elements of their survival from the surrounding environment. Therefore, they committed to the values and customs prevailing in society. According to this principle, the companies are committed to contributing to achieving society's hopes and aspirations. Moreover, participating effectively in the process of its development and well-being (Knudsen et al. 2015).

This voluntary approach to CSR changes governments' roles in relation to the promotion of business, social and environmental practices (Midttun 2005; Matten & Moon 2005). In recent years, corporate social responsibility has turned from voluntary actions into a new approach for business management, which aimed to build and sustain long-term relationships with stakeholders (Steurer, 2013; Altuner et al, 2015). Hence, the governments sprang to employ and support this trend by supporting responsible and sustainable practices of the private sector (Spitzeck 2009).

The assessment of private sector corporates is no longer dependent on only their profitability, reputation or financial positions (Campbell 2007). Modern concepts have emerged to help create a working environment capable of dealing with rapid economic, technological and managerial developments around the world. One of the most prominent of these concepts is the concept of Corporate Social Responsibility (Gao 2011). Therefore, the private sector alerted to its social role and the need to expand its activities to include not only productive ones but also the concerns of the society and environment, taking into account the three pillars of the World Business Council for

Sustainable Development: economic growth, social progress, and environmental protection (Kapoor & Sandhu 2010).

The purpose of this study is to provide a deeper understanding of how governments support the private sector practices of social responsibility, by identifying the roles adopted by the Dubai government represented at Dubai Chamber of Commerce and Industry, to support and promote responsible and sustainable business practices in UAE.

Literature Review

The governments' roles in supporting Corporate Social Responsibility Practices

The global economy has led to many challenges that require governments to seek new frameworks for cooperation with companies and civil society organizations (Albareda et al. 2008). Therefore, governments' performance has changed with the development of communities and business organizations. Recently, governments have played a vital role in improving community conditions by promoting the growth and development of CSR practices and ensuring that these practices carried out in accordance with the customs and norms of society. Government policies have tended to support CSR practices not only in the social field, but also in various areas such as environmental, infrastructure, employment, and human resources development (Thomsen 2004; Peters et al. 2011).

Modern governance has two features. First, it builds on partnerships with the private sector and community during public policy-making and implementation, and second, it relies on approaches such as dialogue, knowledge sharing and volunteerism (Lepoutre et al. 2007).

Fox et al. (2002) in a study for World Bank identified four key roles for governments to stimulate CSR practices:

- Mandating: Government at different levels defines minimum standards for business performance embedded within the legal framework. Moreover, it establishes a system of incentives and accountability.
- Facilitating, through incentives and awards for best responsible practices by private sector companies, such as tax incentives and frameworks of voluntary agreements for supporting civil society.
- Partnership, by dealing with the private sector as stakeholders in achieving sustainable development of society, conducting an endless dialogue with the business community and emphasizing the principle of participation based on mutual benefit.
- Endorsing, through the support, praise, and appreciation of good practices by the government and the media.

The European Commission in 2002 asked the governments of EU Members States to take policy initiatives to foster CSR, through the following (Albareda et al. 2007):

- Enhancing the visibility of CSR and disseminating good practices.
- Exchange of information and experiences in the area of social responsibility with business organizations.
- Developing managerial skills in business practices of CSR.
- Further integrating CSR into education, training, and research.
- Merging corporate social responsibility into community policy.
- Setting rules for accountability, accountability, and evaluation.

Wilson & Olsen (2003) classified government's roles in supporting corporate social responsibility practices in three groups as following:

- Effectiveness: The Government's role in building and strengthening partnerships with business corporations and civil society on the basis of the Win-Win Relationships, a role that harmonizes the market economy.
- Standards: within the framework of this role, the government shall enact legislation and establish regulations governing the practices and applications of social responsibility in society, bearing in mind that the work of companies in this activity is voluntary and therefore its legal responsibility much diluted.

- Methodology: When the government undertakes this role, it must take into account the economic, social and environmental challenges locally and globally. This role related to a clear vision and specific objectives for the government before the plans, programs, and initiatives adopted by the business community.

Zadek (2006) proposed three roles for governments in supporting CSR practices:

- Consolidating the principle of corporate citizenship. Profit should not be the only motivation for business. Society as a whole should consider as stakeholders, and its development must be the duty of all business organizations.
- Establishing the principle of competitive citizenship by encouraging and supporting good and responsible corporate practices, and monitoring rewards for pioneer experiences in this area.
- Adopting the principle of accountability and transparency, through the legislation that regulates the work of the business community.

Another approach to the understanding of CSR public policies is the flexible policy approach introduced by Joseph (2003), in which the role of government viewed as collaborative and facilitated using simple tools and means – always in collaboration with the private sector. In the same context, Post, Preston, and Sachs (2002, 9) emphasize that ‘the capacity of a firm to generate sustainable wealth over time, and hence its long-term value, is determined by its relationships with critical stakeholders’ and ‘any stakeholder relationship may be the most critical one at a particular time or on a particular issue’ (Post, Preston, and Sachs 2002, 8). In addition, Nomin & Parker (2013) indicates that governments are now a stakeholder in the business community and this relationship based on the principle of mutual benefit and interests.

Research Model

According to reviewing the theoretical framework, the researcher suggests a model (Figure 1) that illustrates four basic roles of government to support responsible and sustainable practices of the private sector, which are awareness role, regulatory role, legislative role, and endorsing role. Achieving these roles provide an enabling CSR environment based on responsible business, corporate citizenship, corporate sustainability, corporate accountability, and sharing values and benefits, consequently, contributing effectively to the well-being and sustainable development of society.

Figure 1. A proposed research model

Research Methodology

A qualitative analysis methodology and case study approach was utilized in this study, based on in-depth interviews with those responsible for the Center for Responsible Business (CRB) at Dubai Chamber. Moreover, the information gathered from the website of The Dubai Chamber of Commerce and Industry, “CSR Today” Issued by the Dubai Chamber in Arabic and English, as well as the reports and researches published by the Dubai Chamber about the practices of social responsibility in the UAE. The data collected used to answer the following Research Questions:

1. What are the Values that govern (DCCI) in supporting the responsible and sustainable performance of private sector companies?
2. What are the main activities and events of the (DCCI) to develop sustainable social responsibility practices in UAE society?
3. What are the roles of the Dubai Government, represented by the Dubai Chamber of Commerce and Industry (DCCI) in supporting responsible and sustainable practices of the private sector?
4. What are the challenges facing the Dubai Chamber of Commerce and Industry (DCCI) in applying responsible business practices in UAE society?

The Case Study

The Government of the United Arab Emirates is interested in developing partnerships with civil society, non-governmental organizations, and the private sector (Almatrooshi et al, 2018). This reflected in its Vision 2021, which aims at encouraging businesses and citizens to participate in providing a developed social and economic environment, and building an economy based on knowledge, diversity, innovation, and sustainable development. In this regard, the Government of Dubai was proactive by activating the role of the Dubai Chamber of Commerce and Industry and the Centre for Responsible Business.

Reasons for selecting Dubai Government and Dubai Chamber of Commerce and Industry as Case Study:

- The United Arab Emirates has become an important trading center in the Middle East, ranking first in the Arab Region and 12th in the world at the global competitiveness, according to the 2015 report by the International Institute for Management Development (Yaprak & Thiruvattal 2015).
- The UAE is a leader in the adoption of CSR practices in the Middle East and at the global level. Dubai is the most open source of interest in social responsibility and sustainable development practices. Companies operating in Dubai achieve the highest level of awareness and application of socially responsible and developmental practices in the country (Pick 2014).
- The Dubai Chamber of Commerce and Industry (DCCI) represents the Government of Dubai in establishing the concept of social responsibility and sustainability in the corporate strategies of the UAE business community.

The Dubai Chamber of Commerce and Industry (DCCI)

The Dubai Chamber of Commerce and Industry (DCCI) has developed an integrated approach to solidify the concept of social responsibility and sustainability in the strategies of companies operating in the UAE business community, especially in Dubai. It also sought to identify the latest global trends that would develop responsible and sustainable practices in society.

The Centre for Responsible Business (CRB):

The Dubai Chamber of Commerce and Industry established CRB in 2004 to support and promote the concepts and practices of corporate social responsibility (CSR) and sustainability.

The Center aims to encourage the business community in Dubai to arrogate its responsibility and play a greater role in adhering to the social and environmental needs of the community. The Center for Business Ethics is a leading center with extensive experience in CSR, sustainability, and governance.

The CRB supports companies operating in Dubai to implement responsible business practices in the community that enhances performance and competitiveness among themselves through:

- Promoting the practices of social responsibility, sustainability, and good governance, within the Dubai business community, through the dissemination of knowledge, awareness, and the development of tools that help for the proper application.
- Assessing the performance of the business community in the area of social responsibility, providing direct advice, technical advice and training.
- Encouraging companies to integrate CSR practices into their strategy, management, and operational processes at all levels.
- Measuring and documenting social responsibility practices in Dubai and the UAE.

In the following section, information of the case study will reviewed to answer the Research Questions:

1- The Values Govern DCCI in Supporting CSR Practices: (CSR Today, Jan-Feb 2017)

- **Citizenship**
The business community is a pivotal partner in the development process in the UAE. In recent years, this role has progressed from social responsibility to institutional citizenship to deal with the company as a productive cell in the homeland, has its rights and duties.
- **Partnership**
DCCI has applied the principle of creating shared value, by aligning corporate objectives with social and environmental purposes of CSR and sustainability. It has also pursued policies and practices that enhance corporate competitiveness while at the same time placing societal and environmental issues at the heart of its operational strategies and processes.
- **Sustainability**
Sustainability is a cornerstone of inclusive development. Responsible and sustainable practices are an integral part of modern business strategies and an important factor in their success. Therefore, the Dubai Chamber has launched the "Dubai Sustainability Network" as a platform for companies to exchange information and experiences of responsible and sustainable social practices.
- **Innovation**
Dubai Chamber provides a stimulating environment to develop a knowledge of innovation and support it morally and financially through the adoption and application of ideas and creative initiatives. In the first half of 2015, the Dubai Chamber established an innovation strategy to support the private sector. The strategy included the launch of the Dubai Innovation Metrology Index and the Dubai Innovation Lab to increase the competitiveness of the private sector. Moreover, it launched an electronic platform called "Innovation Pioneers" and a research center that manages ideas and turned them into applied practice.

2- The main Activities and Events of (DCCI): ¹

Table 1. The main activities and events of DCCI

Activities	Description
<i>Research & Case study Directory</i>	The directory of research and case studies highlights the best practices and experiences of CSRs within and outside the UAE. Furthermore, it analyzes and interprets the motivations for applying responsible practices, how they are applied, and their impacts and challenges.
	In 2008, CRB collaborated with Business in the Community (BiTC) and launched Engage Dubai program to facilitate business' role in sustainable development

¹ This question was answered through interviews with officials at the Business Ethics Center at Dubai Chamber and the Dubai Chamber website, online at: www.dubaichamber.com/what-we-do/business-excellence/centre-for-responsible-business

<p><i>Engage Dubai Program</i></p>	<p>through engaging their employees with the community in which they operate.</p> <p>Engage Dubai is a voluntary program; it is a part of an international network of businesses and community organizations working in 23 countries around the world, that collaborate to support the development of healthy and sustainable communities by increasing the quality and quantity of employee volunteering in their local communities. The program aims to increase non-financial strategic contributions to the community by enhancing staff participation in and improving the quality of their communities.</p> <p>The program is the prime in the Middle East. The number of companies joining the program in Dubai reached 140 in 2018. Its employees provide about 6,000 volunteer hours per year for the community's side. The program aims to spread the culture of volunteering among employees and provides a database for companies operating in Dubai to initiate volunteer efforts with their employees in coordination with charitable organizations that seek to recruit volunteers, which helps them to unite their social efforts with the company's strategic objectives. The program has helped companies operating in Dubai to explore successful and effective volunteer areas and opportunities for their employees.</p> <p>The advantages of Engage Dubai for member companies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhancing the company's reputation as a responsible organization, thereby magnifying its competitiveness in the market. • Expanding the markets for the company's products and services by increasing its community network. • Enhancing staff morale, and the company's pride in their achievements, which lead to a quality work environment and maintain staff loyalty. • Increasing the ability of staff to take initiative and cope with change. • Activating the sense of teamwork among employees. • Creating a greater understanding of the issues and challenges that affect society, and its impacts on the environment of the business community and the ways to address them.
<p><i>CSR Label</i></p>	<p>The Dubai Chamber CSR Label launched in 2010 to provide a diagnostic framework for assessing responsible practices of the business community. The acquisition by any company of this award is evidence of its ongoing and concrete efforts in the field of social responsibility and its commitment to developing its responsible practices.</p> <p>The CSR Label designed to meet the needs of companies in the Middle East, UAE, and Dubai in particular. It aims to help companies by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing a clear optional standard for the application of CSR in business practices in Dubai and the UAE. • Reviewing and evaluating corporate strategies and performance in the adoption of social responsibility and sustainable development programs in society. • Providing a tool for all stakeholders to demonstrate the company's commitment to responsible practices and performance within the community. <p>By applying for the Dubai Chamber CSR Label, the companies will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a better understanding of its approach to CSR and a roadmap for further progress. • Conduct a detailed internal assessment of its current CSR activities. • Receive a detailed feedback report on its strengths and opportunities for improvement. • Gain external recognition and extensive promotion for its CSR activities.
	<p>DSN launched in 2011, as an essential platform for the business community, it plays a key role in promoting the concepts of CSR and sustainability by sharing information and best practices about how to implement responsible and sustainable practices in society.</p>

<p><i>Dubai Sustainability Network</i></p>	<p>DSN offers several advantages to its members including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing an opportunity for companies to highlight their responsible practices in Dubai. • Using the logo of the Dubai Sustainability Network on the company’s website. • Communicating and sharing experiences with companies of common interest in CSR, Sustainability, and Governance. • Participating in the periodic multi-stakeholder meetings to discuss issues of sustainability, governance and social responsibility to help companies apply best global practices in this area. • Free participation of two delegates in all paid CSR/Corporate Governance Trainings throughout the year. • Be recognized as DSN members via having speaking opportunities at various CRB and Chamber events and a chance to be part of press releases and media publicity. • Free assessment for the CSR Label.
<p><i>Dubai Dialogue</i></p>	<p>The Dubai Dialogue, which held twice a year, is the largest sustainability conference in Dubai and started its first copy in 2009. The conference includes participants from different industries and sectors to work together for creating a unified vision of social responsibility practices and sustainability in the UAE. The dialogue is a platform for all concerned and interested to discuss all strategies and initiatives available or needed by the business community in the UAE to reach a sustainable and responsible economy.</p> <p>The CRB aims to bring the best creative ideas in the area of social responsibility to the region and expedite dialogue and discussions among academics, practitioners and business leaders on CSR and Sustainability, as well as highlight the most sustainable practices of the global business community.</p>
<p><i>Sustainability Directory</i></p>	<p>The Dubai Chamber Sustainability Directory was set up in 2011 for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Helping individuals and businesses in Dubai to be more sustainable by facilitating their access to sustainable products and services. • Highlighting and promoting companies that offer sustainable products, services, and solutions in the UAE to the local and international audiences.
<p><i>CRB Training</i></p>	<p>The CRB creates a supportive learning environment that helps companies to create new ideas and set ambitious goals for their responsible organizational initiatives. It aims to enhance the learning experience among a wide range of target audience based on business types, industry sectors, employee levels, and governance.</p> <p>The training courses designed to be practical and interactive using the latest technologies and ideas in the organizational culture and learning. These include case studies, role-plays, group activities, videos, and individual exercises.</p>
<p><i>CSR Today Magazine</i></p>	<p>In 2007, CRB issued a monthly publication “CSR Today”; it provides a snapshot of how Dubai businesses are making a difference, thereby raising awareness of and supporting responsible business practices in the UAE.</p> <p>CSR today published in both Arabic and English, as one of CRB early initiatives to promote awareness among companies of the importance and impact of their responsible practices on the development and advancement of society. This publication designed to encourage companies to explore the opportunities that social responsibility practices can offer. In its various print and electronic editions, the newsletter has reviewed several initiatives adopted and launched by the business community. It also introduced several tools, resources, and ideas to help companies implement and integrate CSR programs into their operational processes.</p>

3- The Roles of (DCCI) in Supporting Responsible and Sustainable Practices of the Business Community:²

The researcher identified the main roles adopted by governments to support responsible practices of the private sector, as follows: awareness role, legislative role, regulatory role, and endorsing role. In this context, the roles of the Dubai Chamber of Commerce and Industry to support the best practices of the business community determined as follows:

The Awareness Role

- Issuing specialized publications in the field of social responsibility, such as CSR Today, to introduce the most important social responsibility programs and initiatives and raise awareness of their importance and impact on UAE society and sustainable development.
- Producing publications of volunteer work to announce the needs of charitable organizations for volunteers of their various projects. These bulletins explain the quality of the projects, the fields of volunteering, the number of volunteers required, time and place, and how to participate.
- Launching awareness campaigns in the media to urge the business community and individuals to engage in responsible practices under the slogan "Leave your mark on society".
- Using the DCCI website effectively to raise awareness of the importance of responsible and sustainable business practices.
- Highlighting the leading experiences of businesses in the field of social responsibility and sustainable development by issuing printed and electronic publications entitled "Best Practices" to encourage and support the movements of companies in servicing society.
- Organizing training courses for corporate employees to raise their awareness regarding the importance of social responsibility and its benefits to society and individuals, as well as the reputation of companies and their brands.

The Regulatory Role

The Dubai Chamber of Commerce and Industry (DCCI), represented by the Centre for Responsible Business (CRB), has the following regulatory roles:

- The Research Department of the Center conducts studies aimed at identifying priority areas and projects that should receive the attention and support of state institutions and the business community. Moreover, recognizing the drivers and constraints of social responsibility practices in Dubai, especially those faced by SMEs.
- Organizing volunteer work in Dubai through "Engage Dubai program, which invests the efforts of private sector employees in voluntary activities aimed at developing healthy and sustainable communities. The program provides a database for corporate staff in Dubai and coordinates with charities seeking to recruit volunteers, as well as organizes training courses for these employees to develop their skills in how to manage volunteer activities.
- Dubai Chamber analyzes and evaluates the performance of companies in the area of social responsibility. According to this evaluation, the Chamber sets rules and procedures that encourage leading practices, providing support to companies that have a desire to serve the community but need technical help and training. As well as, it put in place the roles to deprive companies who are ineligible for community service from incentives and support in the business environment.
- Organizing events that discuss issues of social responsibility such as The Dubai Dialogue, which held twice a year, such events invite academics, specialists and international experts

² This question was answered through interviews with officials at the Business Ethics Center at Dubai Chamber and the Dubai Chamber website, online at: www.dubaichamber.com/what-we-do/business-excellence/centre-for-responsible-business

in the field of social responsibility to shed light on their experiences and exchange knowledge between them.

- Preparing guidelines for social responsibility to identify the areas of this responsibility and the criteria for their application, which entitles companies to obtain the Dubai Social Responsibility Award. The guides issued in both Arabic and English, such as:
 - o A guide to sustainable environmental practices and projects.
 - o A guide to health, safety, and well-being in the workplace.
 - o A guide to responsible practices in the labor market.
 - o A guide to developing community investment strategies.
 - o A guide to building partnerships with civil society and the business community.
 - o A guide to best practices and case studies.
 - o A guide to Sustainability Network.
 - o A guide to Dubai Initiatives.

The Legislative Role

- Studying and discussing the laws, and regulations governing the practices of companies in society, to suggest the proper amendments that encourage the business community to adopt practices of social responsibility and sustainable development in the society.
- Dubai Chamber was instrumental in proposing the UAE Commercial Companies Law, which approved in October 2015. This law regulates the relationship between commercial companies and public sector. This law aims to strengthen the legal and regulatory framework of the State to enhance its efforts in sustainable development, to cope with the economic changes taking place in the international environment and the UAE business environment, and the growing role of the business community in supporting community and environmental activities.
- Dubai Chamber is currently studying a law that regulates the work of family businesses and how to benefit from the governance system as one of the economic dimensions of social responsibility; to make the UAE business environment stimulating and suitable for attracting international investments.

The Endorsing Role

DCCI provides an enabling environment for companies to adopt responsible social practices through:

- Highlighting and promoting the prominent corporate social responsibility efforts and practices through the Dubai Sustainability Network reports, the DCCI's website and official pages on social networking, as well as, the traditional media and various forums and events.
- The partnership of the leading companies in the field of social responsibility with the government sector in launching the community and environmental initiatives, and developing strategies for social and sustainable work in the UAE, which reflects the state's confidence and support for these companies and contributes to strengthening their reputation and brands in the market.
- -Candidacy pioneering companies in the field of CSR to receive the Dubai CSR Label, which indicates their continued efforts to develop their responsible practices and provide viable ideas and initiatives that serve society and the environment. This award is an appreciation of the government and society to the leading companies in this field.
- Designing training courses that help companies to understand the key concepts and proper application of social responsibility and sustainable development strategies. The training courses cover a wide range of topics such as; how to plan social responsibility programs, the preparing of social responsibility reports, how to support brand equity by adopting responsible social practices.

4- The Main Challenges Facing Dubai Chamber for Implementing CSR Practices:

- Meeting the needs and aspirations of the state and its citizens in the future, through the preservation of the environment, and the improvement of professional capabilities and functional competence of the state employees (Pick 2014).
- Changing the perception about CSR practices, because some companies still consider social responsibility as a financial donation to some charitable projects. However, charitable and voluntary work is different from social responsibility programs, as its objectives are short-term and may target some rather than all stakeholders. As these actions classified as occasional programs that may offer under certain conditions or religious events if the companies have an adequate budget, it not done periodically.
- Few companies have a specific policy to measure the effectiveness of social responsibility practices. The Dubai Chamber has recently established a performance measurement system in the area of social responsibility, in an attempt to link investment in corporate social responsibility and performance, taking into account the size of the companies, their areas of business, and their essential operational processes.
- Developing leaders in sustainable development through training and developing the employees' skills. DCCI is currently preparing the Sustainability Pioneers program, which aims to prepare specialists to lead sustainable development programs in the society (Rettab 2015).
- SMEs represent about 90% of the business community in Dubai, contributing 35% of the emirate's GDP, and employing about 60% of the total workforce. It plays a key role in society and has enormous impacts on the environment and the community. However, these companies suffer because of their size, weak potential and lack of information, so they became incapable to socially and environmentally responsible practices. They need technical support through training and counseling to help them adopt programs and initiatives that suit their needs and capabilities (Rettab & Maaytah 2015).
- Many companies do not have a specific strategy for social responsibility, but barely a variety of independent initiatives that have no social impact and do not enhance the company's long-term competitiveness. Therefore, DCCI has begun in developing a strategy to promote a responsible and sustainable business practices culture in the business environment and to introduce companies to the benefits of seeking responsible and sustainable policies that benefit their business and their community (Rettab et al. 2014).
- Some companies believe that their social responsibility is only towards the community, and does not realize that they include the responsibilities towards their internal audience of employees and stakeholders, headed by customers and consumers. In this concern, DCCI recently launched guidelines for social responsibility that identified areas of responsibility and tools that can used by corporates to integrate and apply responsible business practices into their strategies (Rettab, Ben Brik & Mellahi 2008).

The Case Study Analysis

In this section, the main results of the case study (Dubai Chamber of Commerce and Industry) will reviewed as follows:

- Dubai Chamber of Commerce and Industry (DCCI), adopt an integral strategy for supporting and motivating responsible behavior and ethical investment policies of the private sector. It plays an awareness role; by spreading knowledge of the value of social responsibility and its benefits to the individual and society, The regulatory role; through setting priorities for sustainable development and the prime areas of interest to be supported by business. Also the legislative role by proposing laws and setting regulations, which organize the responsible practices of the business community. Finally, the endorsing role by; supporting the pioneering experiences in CSR, providing technical guidance for businesses in this field, and maintaining effective partnership with the private sector to serve and develop society.

- Dubai Chamber adopts a comprehensive strategy to support the practice of corporate social responsibility and sustainability practices. It does not focus only on social challenges but develops an effective and comprehensive CSR strategies and policies. Therefore, it attaches concern to the issues of environment and sustainable development, innovation, productivity, occupational health and safety in the workplace, and responsible practices in the labor market towards the stakeholders.
- Dubai Chamber Promotes CSR as an opportunity and competitive advantage for business, as it embraces a win-win relationship with the private sector. Therefore, businesses adopting CSR practices consider as an effective marketing strategy to support the value of their brands in the market.
- The Dubai Chamber plays a pivotal role as a link between the private sector and the government sector and sets the framework for effective partnership between these two sectors and other stakeholders in the community. This partnership allows for dialogue and exchange of experiences among companies of common interest in CSR, sustainability, and governance. Furthermore, the partnership with international organizations in the field of CRS allows DCCI to use global expertise, and to take advantage of the best international practices in this area.
- The Dubai Chamber provides a promising environment for innovation by adopting and implementing creative ideas and initiatives that provide productive and innovative solutions to the problems and challenges facing the community, to cope with the rapid growth witnessed by Dubai and to confirm its reputation as the best destination for international business.
- The Dubai Chamber has been keen to carry out studies and adopt systematic work planned based on the current and future needs of the community, and involve stakeholders in the development of strategies for social action and sustainable development. As well as seeking to support small and medium enterprises in identifying and strengthening their social responsibility strategies, as these companies are the mainstay of the national economy in the UAE.

Conclusion

The changing global economic system, characterized by increasing corporate influence and dominance over the economies of countries, has led to many challenges that require governments to pay attention to the application of CSR practices, through the partnership with the private sector, as a stakeholder in the sustainable development of society. Hence, in a globalized economy, governments must adopt practices that are consistent with their social circumstances, their organizational and political structures, their economic growth, and the nature and size of the business community. Moreover, it should not be isolated from global economic variables and challenges such as globalization, competitiveness standards, global quality standards, corporate citizenship, governance, and others.

CSR is no longer considers as voluntary efforts to serve and develop the community, but it turns from social responsibility to corporate citizenship, so that companies treated as a pivotal partner in the development process. In addition, companies adopt clear and specific social responsibility strategies that have many advantages including strengthening their reputation, enhancing employee loyalty, increasing customer satisfaction, building strong relationships with governments, improving quality and productivity, and consequently increasing their economic efficiency.

The Government of Dubai's experience in supporting and developing the responsible and sustainable practices of the private sector is a successful model in the UAE and the Arab region. It has succeeded in establishing an effective partnership with this sector, based on the principle of the win-win situation. It has embraced a comprehensive strategy to support these practices through a methodology based on inclusiveness, integration, and sustainability, by converging not only social challenges but also economic, environmental, educational and research hurdles. In addition, it

utilizes and applies the creative ideas and initiatives, that offer innovative solutions for existing and future challenges that society may face.

The outcomes of this study will help the governments strengthen their roles as an intermediary among all stakeholders, identify initiatives to be launched and procedures that should be improved to encourage companies to be more socially responsible. Furthermore, it highlights the most important challenges facing governments in managing CSR practices such as: providing a system for measuring the effectiveness of these practices and their return on investment, developing a clear agenda for CSR investments in partnership with the private sector, focusing on the country's development priorities in the different areas. Finally, the number of researches on this matter in the Arab context is insufficient, so future research should focus on examining policies and operations taken by governments to contribute toward more sustainable CSR environments.

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